

Facilitating Scholarly Communication Analysis: the GoTriple Pipeline

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Abstract

Open Science (OS) infrastructures are reshaping research practices in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). Of particular relevance are the digital solutions for the discovery, access, and reuse of scholarly outputs. GoTriple is a multilingual and user-centered discovery platform developed within the context of European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and is operated by the OPERAS Research Infrastructure. The platform aggregates over 20 million publications, 27 thousand projects, and over 18 million researcher profiles. The objective of GoTriple is to address the fragmentation of SSH resources across Europe.

Building on GoTriple, the FASCA project (Facilitating Scholarly Communication Analysis through GoTriple Pipeline) introduced a data science support service that integrates the GoTriple resources with diverse solutions supporting research and FAIR-compliant publication. Through two pilot studies, FASCA demonstrated the feasibility of data-driven SSH research based on GoTriple. This will inform the design of a sustainable GoTriple Data Science Support Service. This paper presents the project's objectives, technical components, and user-centered approach, highlighting its contribution to enhancing reproducibility, and multilingual analysis and engagement in SSH research.

1. Introduction

Recent advances in Open Science (OS) infrastructures in the context of European Research are transforming how Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) scholars perform research activities relating to the discovery, access, and reuse research outputs. The GoTriple platform is one of the services operating under this umbrella. GoTriple (<https://www.gotriple.eu/>) is a discovery platform co-designed with SSH researchers (De Paoli et al., 2025) to support them in their discovery activities. The platform can be thought of as a large aggregator of Open Access (OA) resources with more than 20 million publications, 27 thousand projects, and 18 million researcher profiles. GoTriple always was intended to be a central access point for discovering and reusing research outputs across a wide range of disciplines in Europe. Its ideation resulted from the consideration that SSH resources and groups are widely fragmented across Europe, and there is a need to bring them together to increase the SSH impact and contribution (Mounier et al., 2018).

GoTriple has been designed with a strong focus on supporting multilingualism (Arasteh-Roodsary et al., 2022) and diversity (De Paoli et al., 2022), with the intent to enable researchers to engage with resources and communities across national and linguistic boundaries. As a platform it also embraces the idea that both the data and associated metadata should be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) (De Santis, 2024). The multilingualism aspect, in particular, is intended both for supporting international collaboration but also as a recognition that a significant part of SSH research is published in national languages. GoTriple currently supports and aggregates publications in all European languages. GoTriple was originally developed as part of the Horizon TRIPLE project in the context of the European Open Science Cloud framework. The platform is one of the services offered by the OPERAS (<https://operas-eu.org/>) Research Infrastructure (RI), whose ambition is to coordinate the effort to support open scholarly communication for SSH in Europe. OPERAS aims to federate technical and non-technical resources to strengthen research accessibility and interoperability.

Building on the GoTriple foundation, the authors of this paper conducted the project FASCA (Facilitating Scholarly Communication Analysis through GoTriple Pipeline). FASCA sought to advance data-driven research in SSH by creating a research environment that integrates multilingual discovery, data science workflows, and personalised research support. This would be achieved by using GoTriple (and the aggregated resources in particular via for example the GoTriple Application Program Interface, API) as source of FAIR data. The proposed pipeline includes support for research query formulation, data retrieval, metadata enhancement, semantic annotation, enrichment, visualisation, and analytical interpretation. Each stage of this process is designed to leverage technological components that enable researchers to produce manuscripts, code, and datasets that comply with FAIR principles. GoTriple's extensive index and freely accessible API make it a natural data source for this, providing diverse scholarly content that is essential for a robust SSH data-driven research. At the same time, the project goal was to consolidate the scientific community around GoTriple to maximise its potential for research reuse, providing them with novel data science tools.

The project had the following central objective: to establish a data science support service dedicated to enabling data-driven research on top of the GoTriple platform. To this end, FASCA did also conduct two pilot research projects. Pilot teams did receive support from the GoTriple Data Science team in the conduction of a discrete piece of research, with the intent also to publish their manuscripts, datasets, and code in a fully FAIR-compliant manner. These pilots served as testbeds for designing and refining the GoTriple Data Science Support Service, which will ultimately enrich the GoTriple ecosystem. More specifically, FASCA pursued three objectives:

1. Building a Data Science pipeline for GoTriple, integrating GoTriple's data (publications, projects, profiles, datasets) with a data science Toolbox (JupyterLab, Neo4j) and enhanced GoTriple functionalities (API, Chatbot), and enabling FAIR-compliant publication of results (through GitHub, Zenodo, or BinderHub).
2. Running research pilots that demonstrate the pipeline in practice, resulting in FAIRified research objects that connect publications, datasets, and code.
3. Developing the GoTriple Data Science Support Service to ensure long-term sustainability of data-driven research support beyond the project's duration.

Moreover, in line with the initial design approach of GoTriple, key aspects of the project work were conducted through user research and user testing. Through these efforts, FASCA aimed to strengthen SSH engagement in data-driven research, and extend the capabilities of GoTriple as a cornerstone infrastructure for open, multilingual, and FAIR scholarly communication.

This paper reports on the results of the project and traces the next steps. The text is organised as follows: (1) first we provide a short review of the state-of-the-art with a focus on contextualising FASCA within the broader SSH research landscape; (2) we will then present the data services, including the jupyterlab, the chatbot and the integration with the knowledge graph; (3) we will then discuss key elements of the work performed with researchers (including pilots, interviews, testing) and present key elements of our communication and dissemination approach.

2. Contextualising FASCA

The integration of computational methods, and data science approaches in SSH research is becoming more and more relevant. Novel disciplinary developments such as Digital Humanities (DH) and Computational Social Sciences (CSS) have to be understood on the back of the use of computational techniques to enhance and sometimes also transform more traditional methods. Amongst other directions of work, this transformation also involves a shift in the way textual data is understood and studied: we have seen a process moving from considering texts (e.g. like a book or a manuscript) entirely as cultural artefacts to instead viewing them as a form of data that can, to an extent, be quantified and studied therefore with computational techniques over than interpretation (Galleron & Idmhand, 2020). This literature review, which does not have the aim to be comprehensive of everything, but rather to provide some context to the FASCA services, will seek to briefly trace the evolution of SSH data science approaches (with specific focus on the humanities), from traditional, small-scale activities to broader data-science methods, including using recent development in Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Large Language Models (LLMs).

2.1. Humanities Computing (Pre-2000s)

For a long period of time the core analytical method for text analysis in traditional humanities was close reading, which relies on identifying the main ideas, structures, and expressions within a limited set of texts. Early computational efforts to research texts, sometimes referred to as "Humanities Computing," focused primarily on search and retrieval activities using databases, often automating early forms of corpus linguistics (Schreibman et al., 2004). The focus was often concentrated on scholarly editing and in building digital repositories for humanities texts. The area could be considered still as focused on text analysis within established disciplines (Presner, 2010).

2.2. Digital Humanities (~2000–2015)

According to some authors the broader process of digitisation taking place across society provided the basis for the advent of the field known as 'Digital Humanities'. This was a consequence of an increased amount of text in digital form becoming available for analysis (Grimmer & Stewart, 2013; Huijnen et al., 2014). The increase of digital text availability was then accompanied by a broader adoption of quantitative techniques for the analysis of larger volumes of text. One direct consequence of this was a challenge to the traditional approach to text analysis based on 'close reading' moving to computer 'reading' (Galleron & Idmhand, 2020). Moretti, in particular, proposed the concept of 'distant reading', with a process of analysis focused on identifying patterns across large corpora (Moretti, 2007).

Some publications (e.g. Panduwawala, 2024) report on diverse computational techniques that were adopted by scholars during this period. For example:

- Dictionary methods: these are ‘rule-based’ approaches that use predefined lists of words or phrases to classify texts into categories.
- Topic modelling: these are machine learning approaches, unsupervised, which identify abstract topics within a corpus. Topic modelling also allows the identification of thematic structures (e.g. DiMaggio et al., 2013).
- Supervised methods: these involve training statistical models on annotated subset of documents (the training set) to predict categories across the entire corpus (Grimmer & Stewart, 2013).

2.3. Further developments (~2015 to Present)

Following the first quantitative turn, the field saw however some return to the original strengths of humanities, however supported by digital tools, with an adoption of a more qualitative and interpretive outlook. Techniques therefore were adopted aligning more with this further shift, also incorporating Artificial Intelligence aspects. A short list of these techniques include:

- Multimodal Analysis: this included a focus on ‘cultural analytics’ (Arnold & Tilton, 2024), where computational methods like computer vision are used for analysing large sets of images and other visual media (Münster & Terras, 2020). Also, Temporal and Spatial/Geospatial data analysis has become more important in this context (O’Murchú & Lawless, 2014).
- Natural Language Processing (NLP): early NLP methods were rule-based (like the dictionaries described earlier). However, over time, NLP applied in DH moved toward the use of machine learning techniques (e.g. Suissa et al., 2021). For example, Deep Learning (DL). DL is a ML technique that can be used to automatically learn features from examples. One relevant example is the BERT algorithm, which can be fine-tuned for domain-specific tasks such as Named Entity Recognition (a specific NLP task).
- Generative AI and Large Language Models: these are the latest innovation (with the advent of chatBots like chatGPT or Claude), and are models trained on very large corpuses of textual material which are capable of generating human-like text based on prompts. LLMs are also capable of some contextual understanding (Arslan et al., 2025; Thüs et al., 2024). LLMs are sometimes used with Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) techniques. RAG enhances LLMs by incorporating external data retrieval before text generation (Arslan et al., 2025; Lewis et al., 2020).

A further important aspect to consider is that the increased adoption of computational methods has been accompanied by some changes around methodological standards. Authors noted that novel computational methods require transparency, reproducibility, and rigorous validation (Birkenmaier et al., 2024; Müller-Hansen et al., 2020). It is particularly in these areas that researchers need to develop the capacity to write and adapt their own code, in order to tailor techniques to domain-specific tasks (Suissa et al., 2021). For achieving transparency there probably also is a need

to reduce reliance on off-the-shelf solutions (often black-boxed) and instead ensure that researchers can understand work with the underlying models (e.g. ML, NLP, LLMs) through coding. Making the source code openly accessible will support open science and FAIR compliant results, also allowing others to inspect, reproduce, and build upon the work.

3. The GoTriple Data Services

It is within the context of the increased relevance of data driven analysis and the adoption of computational methods to textual data, that we should locate the innovations that were created through FASCA. Indeed, the GoTriple platform whilst serving the primary purpose of SSH discovery via a graphical user interface can be thought of as a large resource of textual data and metadata that can be reused for analysis purposes and for new research. The platform has a two-level architecture:

- the ‘core pipeline’ where the data imported from aggregators is ingested, processed and enriched by the platform, and
- the ‘Discovery Platform’, what end users see when accessing the website gotriple.eu

GoTriple harvests data both from aggregators (Isidore, BASE, DOAJ, OpenAIRE, EconStor which deliver metadata harvested from their own sources) and providers like (OpenEdition, Biblioteka Nauki, ETK, ZRC Sazu, Coimbra University, Clarin, Cessda, etc which supply data). This is summarised in Figure 1.

Figure 1. GoTriple architecture and concept

FASCA therefore sought to extend GoTriple and expand to discovery aimed at data analysis. This was intended both at the level of the website/interface through the use of LLMs and a chatbot, as well as at the level of discovery and analysis of resources through programming, the API and the use of knowledge graphs. The following are the key innovations delivered by FASCA:

1. The GoTriple platform was enhanced with a personalised and multiuser JupyterHub that spawns, manages, and proxies multiple instances of the single-user Jupyter notebook server. Through this solution the GoTriple users are able to work in their own coding workspaces on data projects leveraging the GoTriple API for example. JupyterLab is a web-based development environment tailored for notebooks, code, and data manipulation.

2. GoTriple users are now able to access and explore the GoTriple data as graphs through the Neo4j Browser via the GoTriple server or using their own Neo4j Desktop. Neo4j is a graph database system that organizes data as nodes and relationships, forming a network. Neo4j empowers users to manage and explore complex relationships, driving insights and innovation across various domains.
3. The original GoTriple's implementation included specialised components which exposed their functionalities via REST API (<https://api.gotriple.eu>). To facilitate the use of the APIs within FASCA we developed a Python package to ease the interactions with the GoTriple APIs from Jupyter notebooks.
4. GoTriple has been augmented with a notebook style Chatbot, utilising RAG and offering users to analyse their own collections of documents, extracted from GoTriple. This is an emergent use of Large Language Models to work and consume literature, which has shown some potentials for working on e.g. literature reviews (Shor et al., 2025).

In the following pages we will briefly describe each of the above FASCA achievements. Moreover, we will present observations on the 'soft' activities relating to the project conduction including:

1. The piloting activities of the data services with two researchers, whose projects were selected from a public call and internal review.
2. User research activities conducted prior to the technical work and also in the form of user evaluation.
3. Reflections on the communication and exploitation plans of the FASCA solutions for the benefit of the wider SSH communities and GoTriple development.

We will start with presenting the technical results.

3.1. The GoTriple-FASCA JupyterHub and Knowledge Graph Integration

The FASCA Data Science Toolbox provides a browser-based notebook environment that allows researchers to explore, analyse, and visualise GoTriple data directly within the platform, without requiring local installation. The environment integrates data access, analysis tools, and visualisation features in a single workspace designed to support reproducible research workflows. Access is provided via GoTriple authentication, ensuring that each user operates within an isolated personal workspace notebook, data files, and outputs persist across sessions.

The proposed research environment is built upon JupyterHub, providing an interactive and extensible workspace for research. The system also integrates Neo4J as the primary graph database, with the Graph Data Science (GDS) module enabled to support advanced graph analytics and machine learning workflows. Each user operates within an isolated environment, ensuring data security and reproducibility. The integrated notebook environment enables researchers to conduct data-driven analyses within a single browser-based workspace, reducing technical setup requirements while supporting transparent and reproducible research workflows.

The environment includes predefined templates with examples, lowering the entry barrier for researchers and promoting best practices. For collaboration and version control, users can publish notebooks to external Git repositories (GitHub, GitLab) via the official JupyterLab Git extension. They can then publish this via Zenodo for FAIRification. An instruction guideline was also prepared for the users for this important step, for making their code FAIR.

The platform also incorporates GoTriple branding to ensure a coherent user experience within the GoTriple-aligned environment. The paper will now go into more details on the JupyterHub environment, presenting what are the main step-by-step activities that a user can perform.

3.1.1. Accessing the Notebook Environment

The user can access the GoTriple-FASCA environment through a web browser by logging in with their GoTriple credentials, from the GoTriple platform. After authentication, they are redirected to the JupyterHub interface (Figure 2), which serves as the main workspace for running notebooks and managing files.

The interface, is organised into three main areas:

- Top menu bar: controls for running notebooks, managing kernels, and accessing settings
- Left sidebar: file browser, running sessions, and version control panel
- Main workspace: central area where notebooks and outputs are displayed

This layout allows users to open notebooks, view results, and manage multiple analysis files simultaneously.

Figure 2. JupyterHub Interface overview

3.1.2. Running Notebooks

To begin analysis, the user opens one of the provided template notebooks from the file browser. These notebooks demonstrate common workflows such as retrieving GoTriple data. Notebooks are executed sequentially, cell by cell. Some cells may take longer to run when retrieving data or performing graph computation. If errors occur, users are encouraged to review parameters or execution order rather than skipping steps (Figure 3).


```

File Edit View Run Kernel Git Tabs Settings Help About FASCA
+
GoTriple_API_demo.ipynb 48 seconds ago
Name Modified
GoTriple_API_demo.ipynb 48 seconds ago

Authors

[6]: author = get_author("pierre_bourdieu_AF28uAgY3fUlymYPQ4Mm")
      print(author.get("id"))
      if "author_of" in author:
          print(" ".join(author.get("author_of")[:5]) + "...")
Last executed at 2026-02-12 16:46:37 in 439ms
pierre_bourdieu_AF28uAgY3fUlymYPQ4Mm
oai:ijs.pkp.sfu.ca:article_7206, oai:doaj.org_article:0eb25688834c4e409c3ad3d526a6b6e, oai:doaj.org_
le_7539, 10670_1.0eJ5ov...

[7]: authors = search_authors("kevin dan", batch=8, sort="name:asc")
      for author in authors:
          print(author.get("fullname"))
Last executed at 2026-02-12 16:46:40 in 2.08s

Pages Iteration: 1/7 [00:02<00:00, 2.80s/pages]
2026-02-12 16:46:40,673 - INFO - gotriple_helper: Found 8 results
(Kevin Davis)
880-06 Tūsi, Naṣīr al-Dīn Muḥammad ibn Muḥammad, 1201-1274. Bīst bāb dar ma'rifat-i a'māl-i aṣṭurīyāb.
880-07 Yazdī, Abū al-Qāsim ibn Aḥmad. Risālah dar ma'rifat-i quṭb'nāma.
A Michael, Kevin
A'zham, Kevin Syahrū
ABEER H A dar mousa
AKOVI, Kevin Teopista
ALACANTARA, JOHNN KEVIN R.

```

Figure 3. Example notebook from the GoTriple/FASCA environment

The notebooks are provided as structured templates that users can modify by changing parameters, queries, or variables, rather than creating analysis workflows from scratch. As the workflow structure is predefined, analyses remain easy to follow and can be rerun using the same sequence of steps, supporting transparent and reproducible research.

3.1.3. Data Access and Graph Analysis

Within notebooks, GoTriple data can be retrieved using a helper package (see later for description) that simplifies interaction with platform APIs. This allows users to search and retrieve objects, including documents and projects directly inside the analysis environment.

The environment also includes an integrated Neo4j graph database. Users connect to Neo4j from notebooks only, using the official Python driver. The returned results are rendered directly in the notebook as interactive visualisations (Figure 4 example). Each user works within a dedicated graph space, ensuring that experiments and analyses do not affect other users. Graph data can be created, modified, visualised, and rerun across sessions.

Figure 4. Example graph visualisation output

3.1.4. Saving and Versioning Work

All notebooks and files are saved automatically within the user workspace and remain available when the user reconnects. The environment also includes optional Git integration, allowing users to track changes, commit versions, and push notebooks to external repositories such as GitHub or GitLab. This allows for lightweight version control and supports reproducibility without requiring command-line interaction. Users can end a session simply by saving files and closing the browser. Their workspace remains available for future sessions.

This functionality also supports alignment with FAIR research principles. By enabling notebooks to be versioned, shared, and archived in external repositories, researchers can ensure their workflows remain findable, accessible and reusable. Integration with repository services such as Zenodo allows versioned releases of notebooks to be assigned persistent identifiers (DOIs) facilitating citation and transparent reuse of research outputs.

3.2. GoTripleHelper

GoTriple provides public search APIs to retrieve its content. The APIs expose the metadata indexed in the GoTriple search index for the three main classes of objects managed by the platform: documents, projects, and researcher profiles. These data are acquired from various sources and enriched through multiple strategies during the processing phase of the GoTriple pipeline.

All GoTriple content is indexed using Elasticsearch, a well-known open-source search engine. The capabilities of the GoTriple APIs are therefore closely linked to the features and query syntax of Elasticsearch. The API documentation is available in Swagger/OpenAPI format at <https://api.gotriple.eu/api/documentation>. Responses can be returned in both JSON and JSON-LD formats.

Finally, new endpoints compatible with the Scientific Knowledge Graphs Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF) have been implemented during the ATRIUM research project (<https://atrium-research.eu/>). Currently, the `/products` and `/grants` endpoints of this open standard are available.

To lower the barrier to accessing these APIs from within the FASCA environment, a dedicated Python package `gotriple_helper` was developed as part of the project. It acts as a thin wrapper around HTTP requests to the GoTriple API, exposing convenient Python functions to retrieve and search GoTriple objects without requiring users to manually handle pagination, nested JSON structures, or HTTP configuration.

The helper supports all major GoTriple object types through a consistent interface:

- Documents: `get_document(id)`, `search_documents(query, filters, sort, batch)`
- Authors: `get_author(id)`, `search_authors(query, filters, batch)`
- Projects: `get_project(id)`, `search_projects(query, filters, batch)`
- Users: `get_user(id)`, `get_users(ids=[...])`

For search endpoints, the package automatically handles pagination by iterating over result pages and returning a consolidated list. It can be configured from within a notebook via `set_url(...)` to point to the production API, `set_timeout(...)` to control request timeouts, and `set_with_logs(True/False)` to enable optional logging. Search functions accept a text query, optional filters as key/value lists, and a batch parameter controlling the number of results fetched per page. Because searches may return large result sets, users are encouraged to start with small batch sizes while exploring, and to refine queries and filters before scaling up.

The package is distributed as an internal library within the FASCA JupyterHub environment and is available directly in the provided notebook templates, where common usage patterns, including deduplication, batching, and progressive exploration, are demonstrated.

3.3. The GoTriple-FASCA notebook

Developing applications that rely on LLMs is a moving target: models, APIs, and best practices evolve very quickly, often requiring continuous adaptation. Building stable, reliable systems in this landscape demands flexibility, iterative design, and an acceptance that constant evolution is the norm. There also is a risk of investing in a specific application, finding a few months later that its concept is obsolete. As FASCA was initiating, new concepts relating to the consumption of literature with LLMs were becoming available, including a recent approach tailored to the idea of allowing users to interact with specific collections of documents via a chatbot/RAG, of which the most known example is likely NotebookLM, but there exist also Open Source versions where the source code is available (e.g. Kotaemon).

These solutions could be (in simplified terms) thought as LLM-driven literature research and note-taking tools, where users can upload a set of sources (a collection of documents) and ask questions within a chat-type form of interaction. This example of service seemed of particular

relevance within the context of FASCA, where in earlier discussions among the team we realised it would be possible to move away from LLM-based solutions encompassing discovery across the entirety of the GoTriple material (which requires substantial processing of data, i.e. processing millions of records, and it would be more feasible in the context of a larger project), allowing the user to move toward a more targeted discovery process on a selection of material they previously gathered from the platform, and these could potentially be complemented by additional user sources. The chatbot therefore adopted this design format and concept.

The GoTriple chatbot is available for users upon sign-in into the platform. In other words, it is a service that requires a GoTriple account. When the user has not previously created notebooks (i.e. first-time users or all notebooks have been deleted), they land on a welcome page highlighting the chatbot’s value propositions (Figure 5).

Figure 5. GoTriple chatbot landing page for first time users

Clicking on the “Create your first notebook” button leads the user to an empty notebook where users can start adding their first sources (“Add sources”). From here the user can choose to:

- A. start adding sources; or
- B. close, leave the notebook empty, and come back at a later time. In this case, the notebook will have a placeholder name: Untitled notebook

When the user has existing notebooks, the welcome page is no longer available and they land on their chatbot dashboard, where the current notebooks are available (Figure 6).

Figure 6. GoTriple chatbot landing page for returning users

The user can open a notebook by clicking on the entire notebook card (e.g. the whole card named ‘AI in Psychology’). A secondary interaction occurs with the options button (three dots). Clicking on this button does not open the card but rather a dropdown in which the user can choose to rename or delete the notebook.

The “Add sources from reading list” button in the left-hand panel opens a multi-step modal. Through this, the user can select documents to import from one or several of their GoTriple reading lists (this is a separate new GoTriple feature, not implemented within FASCA). Once imported and processed, these documents become “sources” in the context of the chatbot.

Figure 7. Sources and document selection

The source is successfully processed and can be used for chatting (Figure 6). A processed source is checked by default. By clicking the options button, users can choose to view the source’s details (GoTriple metadata) or to remove it from the notebook. Sources with free full texts appear with the PDF icon. Sources without full texts lack this icon and they are based merely on the metadata available (Figure 7) on their corresponding GoTriple pages (i.e. abstract).

Figure 8. Metadata display

From here on the user will be able to chat with the documents (Figure 8) of a reading list and converse with the chatbot.

Figure 9. Conversation page

Conversation starters are predefined prompts or clickable suggestions shown to users at the beginning of a chat or during periods of inactivity. They are designed to:

- Encourage engagement
- Guide users toward common use cases
- Reduce friction in starting an interaction
- Showcase the chatbot's capabilities

When the user clicks on one of the conversation starters, the text area is automatically populated with the selected text and the request is sent to the chatbot, without any further interaction from the user. Users can also ask the chatbot to return data in structured JSON format (Figure 9).

Based on the content of the first document, here are the most frequently mentioned concepts and their frequency of occurrence:

```
json
{
  "document": "Drawing a Laugh",
  "concepts": [
    { "term": "repetition", "occurrences": 17 },
    { "term": "comic timing", "occurrences": 13 },
    { "term": "visual exaggeration", "occurrences": 10 },
    { "term": "anticipation", "occurrences": 9 },
    { "term": "pattern disruption", "occurrences": 7 },
    { "term": "slapstick", "occurrences": 6 }
  ]
}
```

These terms appear consistently across sections discussing the mechanics of cartoon humor. Let me know if you'd like **definitions, relevant excerpts, or a structured summary of where these concepts appear** in the document.

Based on the content of the first document, here are the most frequently mentioned concepts and their frequency of occurrence:

Cartoon humor. Let me know if you'd like **definitions, relevant excerpts, or a structured summary of where these concepts appear** in the document.

Figure 9. Response in JSON format

4. User Recommendations, Pilot Studies and User Testing

It is within the context of the increased relevance of data driven analysis and the adoption of computational methods to textual data, that we should locate the innovations that were created through FASCA. Indeed, the GoTriple platform whilst serving the primary purpose of SSH discovery via a graphical user interface can be thought of as a large resource of textual data and metadata that can be reused for analysis purposes and for new research. The platform has a two-level architecture:

- the ‘core pipeline’ where the data imported from aggregators is ingested, processed and enriched by the platform, and
- the ‘Discovery Platform’, what end users see when accessing the website gotriple.eu

GoTriple harvests data both from aggregators (Isidore, BASE, DOAJ, OpenAIRE, EconStor which deliver metadata harvested from their own sources) and providers like (OpenEdition, Biblioteka Nauki, ETK, ZRC Sazu, Coimbra University, Clarin, Cessda, etc which supply data). This is summarised in Figure 1.

4.1. Initial User research

Prior to starting the technical development an initial phase of user research was performed both through the qualitative interview of a small number of potential users as well as via desk research. Working from the predefined GoTriple user segments (researchers, students, public institution staff, policy makers, NGO members, private company professionals, journalists, and citizens, as presented in <https://www.gotriple.eu/about>), we used desktop research (including user guides and platform documentation) to map out hypothetical goals and workflows for each role. This gave us a theoretical foundation for how each user type might interact with digital discovery platforms through data services. We then conducted four target interviews with real users (all researchers which are for FASCA the priority target) to test these assumptions and gather additional insights. By analysing both the desktop research and interview findings, we identified common patterns of use and challenges across different user types. This helped us pinpoint key user needs and translate them into concrete functionality recommendations for the platform. This work gave us a list of possible features and use cases. The underpinning user research and rationale about this work was detailed in an internal “User Needs – Insights & Recommendations” report.

Not all the identified features and the more specific Use Cases would be served by the FASCA solutions. But this helped us better understand the current user needs, create a list of Use Cases that could be addressed in the future, and provided guidance for current technical development. Two examples of these features are shown below in Tables 1 and 2 in total we identified 9 broader groups/features, underpinning diverse user needs as resulting from the research, including: (1) Content Discovery and Aggregation; (2) Collaborative Editing and Workspace Management; (3)

Translation, Summarization, and Validation; (4) Data Management, Analysis, and Reformatting; (5) Knowledge Management and Archival Systems; (6) Knowledge Management and Archival Systems; (7) Professional Development, Networking, and Identity Integration; (8) Stakeholder Engagement, Public Outreach, and Campaign Management; (9) Role-Specific / Specialized Functionalities.

Feature	Content Discovery and Aggregation
Specific Needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● AI-powered semantic search across scholarly articles, policy briefs, news, and other sources ● Conversational interfaces for knowledge graph exploration and querying ● Interactive knowledge graph visualization with personalized filtering and navigation ● Transparent data provenance tracking and source verification - Open-access data aggregation from institutional/public repositories (e.g., CORE, BASE, Zenodo) ● Automated reference extraction and citation management - Bookmarking, annotation, and modular content aggregation (for coursework, literature reviews, etc.)

Table 1. Example of feature from user research

Feature	Data Management, Analysis, and Reformatting
Specific Needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Robust data upload and management modules supporting FAIR standards ● AI-driven text/data analysis (knowledge graph / RAG + chat interface) ● Automated document reformatting to enhance readability (improved spacing, headings, segmentation) ● Tools for structured data extraction, tabulation, and integration with knowledge graphs ● Dynamic dashboards and real-time alerts for new data availability

Table 2. Example of feature from user research

Based on the user research, 60 possible Use Cases with direct focus on the use of JupyterHub and the Knowledge Graph were then isolated and prioritised. Of these 27 were considered out of scope through a discussion between the user researchers and the technical team. The remaining 33 were then considered, but again prioritised via a MoSCoW (Must have, Should have, Could have, and Won't have) decision making template. Some examples to illustrate the logic are presented in Table 3.

Feature	Tool	Required	Justification from "User Needs - Insights & Recommendations"	MoSCoW
Multi-user management and isolated work environments	Jupyter Hub	Yes	Researchers and students need separate workspaces to manage their projects.	Must Have
Storage and sharing of notebooks among researchers	Jupyter Hub	Yes	Essential for collaborative research and group projects.	Should Have
Execution of automated workflows for GoTriple data transformation	Jupyter Lab	Yes	Helps maintain consistency in data processing and document structuring.	Could Have
Automated cloud-based backup and versioning of notebooks	Jupyter Hub	No	Data should be stored in external repositories (e.g., Zenodo, GitHub).	Won't Have
Automatic generation of graph schemas from GoTriple metadata	Graph tool	Yes	Helps researchers structure their data efficiently for scholarly communication.	Must Have
Interactive analysis of relationships between entities	Graph tool	Yes	Key for understanding scholarly networks, policy influencers, and social movements.	Should Have

Table 3. Example of relevant FASCA UCs from the research

4.2. Pilot activities

The validity of the data science solutions for GoTriple, as well as the approach for offering support to researchers provided by expert data scientists, were assessed via piloting and user testing (where the solution was available on time). The pilot testing was a key component of the project, and it entailed first an open call to the scientific community with the selection of two project ideas run by external researchers. Applications were received by June 2025. Following this an internal selection process took place, with the official start of the piloting taking place from September 2025 onwards.

Title: Open Call for Applications – Pilot Projects with GoTriple Data Services

Introduction

GoTriple Data Services invites researchers in the fields of Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) to participate in an open call for pilot projects. We offer a unique opportunity to leverage the innovative GoTriple Data Services research infrastructure, built on the GoTriple platform, to conduct data-driven research in the area of scholarly communication within the context of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). GoTriple Data Services aims to support interdisciplinary research by integrating GoTriple resources with advanced data analysis tools.

Two projects will be selected for support in the program.

[full text of the call can be consulted here: <https://gotriple.eu/data-services/openCall2025>]

Nine applications were received, and two projects were then selected based on their merit and strategic alignment with the FASCA objectives of piloting the novel solutions.

1. Gotriple for Raising Environmental Awareness In Social Sciences and Humanities (GREANISSH)
2. Exploring Scholarly Communication in Social Sciences and Humanities with a reproducible approach: The GoTriple use case

4.2.1. The GREANISSH Pilot Project

The first FASCA pilot explored the potential of GoTriple data services to analyse the presence, evolution, and impact of environmental topics across Social Sciences and Humanities research, with a particular focus on Translation Studies. The project aligns with broader Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by investigating how environmental issues are addressed within SSH scholarship and by promoting awareness of sustainability-related research themes. At the same time, the pilot also examines the broader thematic structure of the analysed corpus, allowing environmental topics to be contextualised within the wider landscape of research themes present in Translation Studies and related SSH fields.

The pilot combined dataset creation with computational analysis in order to examine how environmental discourse appears within SSH literature and how it relates to other thematic areas represented in the corpus. The first stage involved preparing a multilingual dataset of Open Access publications from Translation Studies journals. This included identifying relevant journals, harvesting and cleaning metadata records, and preparing structured datasets suitable for further analysis. In addition to metadata collection, the project compiled a corpus of full-text articles that enables more advanced text-based research on environmental themes as well as broader thematic exploration of the corpus.

The second stage focused on analysing the collected material using computational approaches. This involved iterative query refinement, keyword analysis, and the exploration of thematic patterns across the dataset. The study examined the distribution of research themes across articles, as well as characteristics of authorship. It also investigated the internal structure of the corpus, including thematic clusters, relationships between research topics, and patterns of co-occurrence among different scholarly themes.

The pilot produced several concrete research outputs. These include a curated list of journals in the field of Translation Studies together with a structured metadata dataset describing articles published in these venues, as well as a corpus of full-text publications collected for further analysis. Initial analytical results were summarised in a working draft addressing environmental sustainability and other thematic trends in fully Open Access Translation Studies journals. In addition, the metadata describing the compiled corpus will, where possible, be integrated with the GoTriple platform, which will increase the visibility and potential reuse of the collected materials within the SSH research community. The scripts used for collecting, processing, and analysing the data will also be made publicly available to support transparency and reproducibility of the research.

4.2.2. Exploring Scholarly Communication in Social Sciences and Humanities with a reproducible approach Pilot

The second pilot focused on enabling reproducible, data-driven research workflows based on the GoTriple platform by developing computational access to its data and demonstrating methodological approaches for reuse. The pilot builds on existing practices from the GLAM (Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums) domain, particularly the “Collections as Data” paradigm, and adapts these approaches to scholarly communication in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH).

The primary objective of the pilot was to develop reusable analytical workflows that facilitate exploration and evaluation of GoTriple data. Central to this work was the creation of a collection of Jupyter Notebooks that demonstrate how to access the GoTriple API, extract metadata, and conduct reproducible analyses. By combining executable code, documentation, and visualisations, these notebooks illustrate practical methods for analysing large SSH metadata collections. The workflows were designed following best practices developed by the international GLAM Labs community, with the aim of lowering the technical barrier for SSH researchers interested in computational approaches.

Methodologically, the pilot combined metadata extraction with exploratory data analysis and data quality assessment. Particular attention was given to examining the structure and completeness of bibliographic metadata as well as to analysing the diversity of languages represented in the GoTriple catalogue. The project also explored keyword distributions, language representation, and algorithmic perspectives on metadata heterogeneity, reflecting broader research questions concerning multilingualism and representation in SSH scholarly communication.

The pilot also explored the integration of GoTriple data within broader Open Science infrastructures. In particular, the project examined possible connections with European initiatives such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and the SSH Open Marketplace in order to demonstrate how GoTriple datasets and analytical workflows can be shared and reused within the wider research ecosystem. These activities support FAIR and CARE data principles by promoting transparency, reproducibility, and interoperability.

As a result, the pilot generated several practical research outputs supporting reproducible research with GoTriple data. These include a collection of Jupyter Notebooks presenting example workflows for analysing metadata diversity and multilingual aspects of the platform. The project also produced a dedicated dataset derived from GoTriple metadata focusing on the multilingual characteristics of the portal. Initial analytical findings have been summarised in a working draft that explores multilingualism in Social Sciences and Humanities catalogues through the analysis of GoTriple. The draft presents early insights into language representation in SSH metadata collections.

4.3. User testing of Chatbot

As part of the project activities we also conducted a think-aloud study to evaluate the early GoTriple chatbot prototype developed within the FASCA project. The aim was to investigate:

- How SSH researchers interact with the chatbot
- How intuitive the interface, notebook system, and source-selection workflow are
- How well the chatbot handles multi-source tasks
- Where participants experience confusion, breakdowns, or trust issues
- What improvements would meaningfully enhance usability and research value

SSH participants (n=8) included domains such as History, Psychology, Business and Games & Arts. Participants represented a mix of research experience and digital fluency. One participant had never used LLMs for research. None specialised in data science or computer science. Participants took part in a 30-minute guided think-aloud session completing typical research tasks (adding sources, summarising, comparing sources, generating citations, and asking questions). Following chatbot interaction, participants completed a brief survey, rating perceived ease of use, usefulness and likelihood of future use. Screen recordings and facilitator notes captured user behaviour, expectations, misunderstandings, and pain points.

While all participants found the interface generally easy to navigate after brief exploration, several areas were identified as needing improvement. While usability ratings were generally high, trust and perceived reliability were more strongly influenced by source handling and response consistency than by interface ease of use alone. The chatbot frequently mishandled source selection and struggled with multi-source tasks, such as understanding which sources participants wished to interact with. Responses were occasionally noted as being inconsistent or incomplete. Navigation issues, unclear system behaviour, and slow loading also disrupted task flow. Despite these challenges, users consistently valued the concept, appreciated features such as “summarisation” and “citation

generation”, and felt the tool had potential, assuming consistency, reliability and transparency improved. Recommendations were then made to improve the chatbot interface and usability, which were then actioned in the subsequent release of the solution.

Based on frequency, severity, and impact on trust and task completion, recommendations were prioritised as follows:

Primary	Secondary
Fix source-selection logic	Expand prompting support + onboarding
Improve multi-source handling and scaling	Enhance citation completeness and metadata fidelity
Add clear Back/Close navigation between pages	Allow for manual language switching/translations within chatbot window
Improve transparency about data sources and limitations	Add a progress bar when loading stalled
Improve scrolling and chat window sizing	—

Table 4. Recommendations from user testing (chatbot)

4. Communication and Exploitation plans after the project

Alongside the user research and piloting, further ‘soft’ activities of the project entailed the definition of a communication plan, and of a plan for exploiting the results within the context of the OPERAS activities. The communication plan identified these priorities:

- Communicate the value: Demonstrate how FASCA’s advanced features empower SSH researchers to perform comprehensive, data-driven analysis.
- Educate and train: Communicate tailored training materials and hands-on sessions that cater to various levels of expertise—from newcomers to advanced users.
- Foster community: Build a supportive network through interactive webinars, forums, and pilot studies that showcase best practices in Open Science.

Alongside this, key groups were also identified for dissemination

- Inexperienced Researchers and Postgraduates: Need introductory guidance on navigating GoTriple and understanding the basics of integrated data science tools.
- Experienced Scholars and Research Data Managers: Require advanced training on customising workflows, utilising interactive notebooks, and leveraging knowledge graphs and analytics tools for deeper analysis.
- Interdisciplinary Teams and Project Managers: Focus on linking research outputs (publications, data, code) with specific goals. (Ideally SDGs and ensuring compliance with FAIR principles.)

The channels presented in Table 5 were identified for primary dissemination of the project results.

Channels	Key Examples
Online Platforms	Project Website and GoTriple Portal: Central hub for project updates, resource libraries, training module links.
	Social Media: targeted posts on OPERAS SM channels sharing plans, upcoming training sessions, and feature highlights.
	Academic Forums and Research Networks: Engagement in Open Science communities to promote discussions and share best practices.
	GitHub Repo with examples of source code
Direct Outreach	Webinars and Workshops: Live sessions with demonstrations, Q&A segments

	and hands-on training to familiarise users with new workflows.
Offline Engagement	Conferences and Academic Workshops: Present / demo training case studies at SSH and Open Science events to garner broader interest and feedback

Table 5. Channels

Figure 10 shows an example of communication from the GoTriple platform, describing FASCA tools. Figure 11 shows instead an example of communication via social media (LinkedIn).

Enhance your research via GoTriple with FASCA's Advanced Science Tools

FASCA is a new initiative to enrich GoTriple's advanced services. It will provide SSH researchers with the tools they need to unlock the full potential of GoTriple's multilingual data. Streamline your research, collaborate more effectively, and ensure your work is FAIR-compliant with our powerful support services.

FASCA has received funding through the [OSCARS project](#) via the European Commission's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101129751

How FASCA improves GoTriple

The purpose of the FASCA project is to **enrich GoTriple with a set of specialised services**, to **enable data-driven research** based on the rich amount of information offered by the platform. By integrating **advanced data science tools** into the GoTriple platform and with the support of a dedicated team of data scientists, FASCA will support **multilingual research guided by data**, enabling the publication of **FAIR-compliant outputs**. Thanks to FASCA, whether you're conducting complex analyses or aiming to make your research more impactful, GoTriple is your partner in innovation.

Figure 10. FASCA communication example (1)

OPERAS Research Infrastructure
2,228 followers
9mo • 🌐

How can [#GoTriple](#) [#DataScience](#) services help you?

Whether you need to analyse data, publish FAIR-compliant results, or collaborate with colleagues, FASCA offers the tools and services to help you succeed.

FASCA combines the power of GoTriple's comprehensive discovery platform with advanced data science tools to support SSH researchers in multiple stages of their research journey.

Keep in touch about FASCA's evolution: <https://bit.ly/FASCA-form>

[#FAIR](#) [#DataScience](#) [#DataServices](#)

Stay tuned for deeper insights into:

- Smart tools like the GoTriple AI assistant, API, and annotation features.
- Powerful analysis platforms including JupyterLab and Next.
- Seamless and FAIR publishing workflows for research data and outputs.

FASCA FACILITATING SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION ANALYSIS THROUGH GOTRIPLE PIPELINE

GoTriple

OPERAS Services

Funded by the European Union

Figure 11. FASCA communication example (2)

Dissemination will become more intense as the pilots are concluded and the FASCA tools are finalised and ready for wider adoption.

5. Conclusion

The FASCA project integrated advanced data science workflows into the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) research ecosystem through the GoTriple platform. By extending GoTriple beyond its original role as a multilingual discovery service, FASCA has introduced a pipeline that enables researchers to move from resource discovery to computational analysis in a FAIR-compliant manner. This evolution reflects broader trends in SSH, where digital infrastructures and computational methods are increasingly central to scholarly practice.

The technical innovations (JupyterHub environment, Neo4j-based knowledge graph integration, a Python package for GoTriple API interaction) provide researchers with practical tools to be used for data-driven research using GoTriple as data source. These solutions empower scholars to engage with complex datasets and data analysis. The addition of an LLM-powered chatbot further illustrates how emerging AI technologies can support literature exploration and knowledge synthesis, offering new ways for scholarly communication. Through interviews, pilot studies, and usability testing, the project has also sought to capture and test the diverse needs of SSH researchers and translate them into actionable design. The pilots validated the feasibility of the pipeline, while user testing highlighted areas for refinement.

Looking ahead, the sustainability of the GoTriple Data Science Support Service will be critical. Continued investment in training, community engagement, and open-source dissemination will ensure that the tools developed under FASCA remain relevant for the SSH community. Moreover, the project's emphasis on FAIR principles makes the GoTriple dataservice relevant for multilingual scholarly communication in Europe.

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